

Wave-Like Dark Matter: Compatibility with Current Experiments and Observations

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Abstract

This paper evaluates the compatibility of the wave-like dark matter (WDM) framework with established quantum mechanics experiments and gravitational phenomena. We revisit foundational experiments such as the double-slit experiment, quantum entanglement, and the Casimir effect, as well as cosmological and gravitational tests. The analysis demonstrates that WDM not only reproduces known results but also provides novel insights into the underlying mechanisms of these phenomena.

1. Introduction

The wave-like dark matter (WDM) model offers a unified framework for quantum mechanics and gravity, as developed in previous papers of this series. Here, we examine whether WDM aligns with existing empirical evidence, focusing on experiments that are pillars of quantum mechanics and gravitational theory.

Experiments discussed include:

- The **double-slit experiment**, demonstrating wave-particle duality.
- Quantum entanglement** experiments, testing nonlocal correlations.
- The **Casimir effect**, probing quantum field fluctuations.
- Cosmological tests of general relativity and dark energy.

We show that WDM accommodates these results while offering explanations rooted in the scalar field Φ .

2. Revisiting Key Quantum Experiments

2.1. The Double-Slit Experiment

Experimental Result

The interference pattern observed in the double-slit experiment supports wave-particle duality: particles exhibit wavelike behavior when not measured but behave like particles upon observation.

WDM Interpretation

In the WDM framework, the scalar field Φ governs interference through its oscillatory nature. The superposition of field solutions through the slits is:

$$\Phi_{\text{total}}(\vec{r}, t) = \Phi_1(\vec{r}, t) + \Phi_2(\vec{r}, t),$$

resulting in an intensity pattern:

$$I(\vec{r}) = |\Phi_{\text{total}}|^2 = |\Phi_1|^2 + |\Phi_2|^2 + 2\text{Re}[\Phi_1^* \Phi_2].$$

The WDM field propagates wave-like disturbances, while particle-like behavior emerges due to localized excitations in Φ . Measurement collapses the WDM oscillation to a single eigenstate, consistent with the Born rule.

2.2. Quantum Entanglement

Experimental Result

Entangled particles exhibit correlations that violate Bell's inequality, suggesting instantaneous nonlocal interactions.

WDM Interpretation

The entangled state is represented by coupled scalar field solutions:

$$\Phi_{\text{entangled}} = \Phi_A(\vec{r}_A, t)\Phi_B(\vec{r}_B, t),$$

where Φ_A and Φ_B describe the fields for particles A and B. Measurement of one particle induces a rapid field realignment, preserving conservation laws and producing the observed correlations.

This mechanism respects locality in field propagation but allows nonlocal correlations as a consequence of the underlying field coupling.

2.3. The Casimir Effect

Experimental Result

Two closely spaced conducting plates experience an attractive force due to suppressed quantum vacuum fluctuations between them.

WDM Interpretation

In the WDM model, vacuum fluctuations are perturbations in the scalar field Φ . The presence of boundaries modifies Φ 's allowed modes, reducing the energy density between the plates relative to the surrounding space.

The Casimir force per unit area is given by:

$$F_c = \frac{\pi^2 \hbar c}{240 a^4},$$

where a is the separation between the plates. This prediction, derived from WDM field constraints, is consistent with experimental data.

3. Compatibility with Gravitational Phenomena

3.1. Gravitational Lensing

Observational Result

Massive objects bend light, consistent with general relativity's prediction of curved spacetime.

WDM Interpretation

In the WDM framework, light bends due to gradients in the scalar field Φ , which mediates both gravitational and quantum effects. The bending angle θ is derived from the effective potential V_{eff} :

$$\theta \sim \int \nabla_{\perp} \Phi ds,$$

where $\nabla_{\perp} \Phi$ represents the transverse gradient of the field. This matches general relativity's predictions for lensing effects without invoking curved spacetime.

3.2. Cosmic Expansion

Observational Result

The universe is expanding at an accelerating rate, attributed to dark energy.

WDM Interpretation

The expansive dynamics of the scalar field Φ , as derived in Paper 2, naturally lead to an accelerating universe. The energy density associated with WDM oscillations corresponds to the observed cosmological constant Λ .

4. Experimental Validations

4.1. Bose-Einstein Condensates (BECs)

In BEC systems, quantum phenomena manifest on macroscopic scales. The WDM field could be tested by observing how BECs interact with scalar perturbations. Predictions include altered interference patterns under varying scalar field intensities.

4.2. Precision Tests of Quantum Tunneling

Quantum tunneling experiments in high-precision setups could reveal deviations from the standard quantum mechanical tunneling rate, arising from the WDM field's influence.

5. Implications for Future Research

The WDM framework extends our understanding of quantum mechanics and gravity, opening avenues for experimental exploration:

- Unified Predictions:** WDM provides a single-field explanation for phenomena traditionally described by disparate theories.
 - New Experiments:** Testing scalar field dynamics in controlled environments could reveal subtle deviations from established quantum mechanics.
 - Gravitational-Wave Correlations:** Analyzing correlations between gravitational waves and field perturbations could validate the WDM model.
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6. Conclusion

This paper demonstrates the compatibility of the wave-like dark matter (WDM) framework with foundational quantum and gravitational experiments. WDM preserves the results of established experiments while offering a unifying mechanism based on the scalar field Φ . Future work will explore experimental tests to distinguish this model from standard theories.

Keywords: Wave-like dark matter, quantum mechanics, gravitational lensing, Casimir effect, double-slit experiment